

After work up and purification, the desired bisaldehyde **6** was obtained in good yield. During Vilsmeier-Haack reaction on **8a**, a small amount of **9a** and **12a** were also obtained in addition to **6a**.

Attempted crystallization of diformylchromone **6** from methanol by heating under reflux (due to poor solubility) led to the formation of a mixture of compounds. After separation of its components and analysis, the new product was found to be the diacetal **10**. Though 3-formylchromone **1** could readily be crystallized from methanol, the formation of acetal from similar treatment on bischromone **6** encouraged us to study the action of methanol on **6**. The results of the action of methanol on simple aldehyde **1** and bisaldehyde **6** under different conditions are shown in Table 1.

Chromone **1** is usually recrystallised from methanol or ethanol but on prolonged heating in dry methanol under reflux, acetal **2** was found to be formed in very good yield (entries 1, 2). Addition of TsOH reduced the reaction time sharply (entry 3)⁸. But unexpectedly, 3,3'-diformylbischromone **6** gave acetal **10** when heated with ordinary methanol for 20 h (entries 4, 7). When dichloromethane (DCM) was used as a cosolvent to increase the solubility of **6** (ordinary methanol : DCM ::

5 : 1), acetal formation takes place within 10 h (entries 5, 9). Use of dry methanol completed the reaction within 6 h in good to excellent yield (entries 6, 8, 10). Presence of TsOH shortened the reaction time (entry 11).

Treatment of 3-formylchromone **1** with Et₃N in methanol has been studied in detail⁸. Formation of di(chromenone-3-yl)carbinol as one of the products in the above reaction gave us an impetus to study the reaction of triethylamine with bisaldehyde **6** in methanol. On heating **6** (1 eq.) in dry methanol under reflux in the presence of Et₃N (3 eq.) for 7 h and after usual work up, compound **11** was found to be formed in moderate to good yield (entry 12). But using excess Et₃N (10 eq.) the reaction was completed within 4 h (entries 14, 16). When the reaction time was reduced from 4 h to 3 h, a small amount of **12a** was also isolated (entry 13). In aprotic solvent Et₃N fails to react even after prolonged heating (entry 15). Compound **11**, obtained by the deformylation of **6**, was independently synthesized by acid induced cyclisation of β -*N,N*-dimethylamino- α,β -unsaturated ketone **13** (Scheme 2)⁶. Like the previous case⁶, here also the methylene protons in compounds **6b**, **10b** and **11b** (having 4-carbon chain) appear as singlets although in other compounds **6a,c**, **10a,c** and **11a,c** they appear with their usual multiplicities.

Table 1. Treatment of aldehyde **1** and **6** with methanol under different conditions

Entry no.	Substrate	Reaction medium	Time (h)	Product	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1	1a	Dry MeOH	25	2a	78–80 (Lit. ⁷ 80)	90
2	1b	Dry MeOH	22	2b	115 (Lit. ⁷ 116)	85
3	1a	Dry MeOH/TsOH	5	2a	79–80	92
4	6a	Ordinary MeOH	10	Mixture of 10a and 6a		
5	6a	Ordinary MeOH/DCM	6	10a	100–102	60
6	6a	Dry MeOH	5	10a	100–102	80
7	6b	Ordinary MeOH	20	10b	164–166	50
8	6b	Dry MeOH	5	10b	164–166	90
9	6c	Ordinary MeOH/DCM	10	10c	108–110	50
10	6c	Dry MeOH	5	10c	110–112	98
11	6a	Dry MeOH/TsOH	3	10a	100–102	85
12	6c	MeOH/Et ₃ N	7	11c	161–162	60
13	6a	MeOH/Et ₃ N (excess)	3	11a	168–170	40
				12a	148–150	15
14	6b	MeOH/Et ₃ N (excess)	4	11b	212–214	70
15	6c	DCM/Et ₃ N	25	No reaction		
16	6c	MeOH/Et ₃ N (excess)	4	11c	160–162	60

Scheme 2

Experimental

The recorded melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Beckman IR 20A and NMR spectra on a Bruker 300 MHz spectrometer. Ordinary methanol refers to methanol (E. Merck, India) as supplied.

Synthesis of 6,6'-[(α , ω -alkanediol)bisoxy]bis[4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-carbaldehyde] (6a-c). General procedure :

POCl_3 (2 ml, 22 mmol) was injected into dry DMF (2 ml, 26 mmol) under argon atmosphere at 0–5 °C temperature and allowed to stir under this condition for 5 min. A solution of **8** (1 mmol) in dry DMF (8–10 ml) was injected slowly at this temperature. After complete addition, the resultant mixture was stirred under cold condition for 10 min and then allowed to come to room temperature and stirred under this condition for 6 h. The resultant thick reddish reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice (100 g) when a yellow coloured solid appeared. It was filtered, washed with water, dried in air and recrystallised from dichloromethane to afford a light yellow solid **6** in moderate to good yield. After isolation of **6a** from the reaction mixture of **8a**, the remaining mixture was chromatographed using silica gel (100–200 mesh) to get small amounts of **9a** and **12a**.

6a : Yield 300 mg (71%); m.p. 192–194 °C; (Found : C, 65.94; H, 3.95. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8$ requires : C, 65.71; H, 3.84%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3065, 1689, 1661, 1602, 1485, 1464, 1313; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 2.38 (2H, quintet, J 6.0 Hz, CH_2), 4.31 (4H, t, J 6.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 7.35 (2H, dd, J 9.1, 3.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-7}$), 7.49 (2H, d, J 9.1 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-8}$), 7.67 (2H, d, J 3.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-5}$), 8.54 (2H, s, $2 \times \text{H-2}$) and 10.40 (2H, s, $2 \times \text{CHO}$).

6b : Yield 350 mg (81%); m.p. 258–260 °C; (Found : C, 66.61; H, 4.30. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$ requires : C, 66.36; H, 4.18%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3070, 1666, 1591, 1468, 1219; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 2.07 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 4.18 (4H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 7.34 (2H, dd, J 9.0, 2.9 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-7}$), 7.48 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-8}$), 7.65 (2H, d, J 2.9 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-5}$), 8.53 (2H, s, $2 \times \text{H-2}$) and 10.40 (2H, s, $2 \times \text{CHO}$).

6c : Yield 310 mg (69%); m.p. 200 °C; (Found : C, 67.21; H, 4.38. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_8$ requires : C, 66.96; H, 4.50%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3050, 1672, 1610, 1454, 1312; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 1.69–1.76 (2H, m, CH_2), 1.89–1.98 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 4.13 (4H, t, J 6.2 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 7.32 (2H, dd, J 9.1, 2.9 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-7}$), 7.48 (2H, d, J 9.1 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-8}$), 7.64 (2H, d, J 2.9 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-5}$), 8.53 (2H, s, $2 \times \text{H-2}$) and 10.40 (2H, s, $2 \times \text{CHO}$).

9a : Yield 20 mg (5%); m.p. 146–148 °C; (Found : C, 66.14; H, 4.63. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ requires : C, 65.96; H, 4.74%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3350, 3067, 2926, 1688, 1662, 1603, 1487; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 2.32 (2H, quintet, J 5.9 Hz, CH_2), 2.62 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.15 (2H, t, J 5.9 Hz, OCH_2), 4.30 (2H, t, J 5.9 Hz, OCH_2), 6.92 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3'), 7.13 (1H, dd, J 9.0, 2.9 Hz, H-4'), 7.22 (1H, d, J 2.9 Hz, H-6'), 7.32 (1H, dd, J 9.1, 2.9 Hz, H-7), 7.48 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz, H-8), 7.69 (1H, d, J 2.9 Hz, H-5), 8.53 (1H, s, H-2), 10.39 (1H, s, CHO) and 11.85 (1H, s, exchangeable, OH).

12a : Yield 15 mg (4%); mp 148–150 °C; (Found : C, 67.50; H, 4.21. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$ requires : C, 67.34; H, 4.11%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3067, 2926, 1691, 1651, 1603, 1487; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 2.31–2.39 (2H, m, CH_2), 4.26–4.32 (4H, m, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 6.33 (1H, d, J 5.9 Hz, H-3'), 7.28–7.36 (2H, m, H-7 and H-7'), 7.41 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz, H-8'), 7.48 (1H, d, J 9.1 Hz, H-8), 7.59 (1H, d, J 2.9 Hz, H-5'), 7.67 (1H, d, J 2.9 Hz, H-5), 7.84 (1H, d, J 5.9 Hz, H-2'), 8.53 (1H, s, H-2) and 10.39 (1H, s, CHO).

Treatment of 3,3'-diformylbischromone 6 with dry methanol :

Bischromone **6** (0.25 mmol) was heated under reflux in dry MeOH and the progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After refluxing for 5 h, solvent was removed under reduced pressure to get a semisolid mass, which was purified by passing through a silica gel column using 10% EtOAc in benzene as eluent to get a light yellow solid **10**.

10a : Yield 100 mg (78%); m.p. 100–102 °C; (Found : C, 63.50; H, 5.65. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_{10}$ requires : C, 63.27; H, 5.50%); $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3060, 2950, 2880, 2825, 1640, 1620, 1470; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 2.33 (2H, quintet, J 6.0 Hz, CH_2), 3.43 (12H, s, $4 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 4.26 (4H, t, J 6.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{OCH}_2$), 5.62 [2H, s, $2 \times \text{CH}(\text{OMe})_2$], 7.27 (2H, dd, J 9.0, 3.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-7}$), 7.40 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-8}$), 7.60 (2H, d, J 3.0 Hz, $2 \times \text{H-5}$) and 8.09 (2H, s, $2 \times \text{H-2}$).

10b : Yield 110 mg (90%); m.p. 164–166 °C; (Found : C, 63.45; H, 5.88. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_{10}$ requires : C, 63.87; H,

5.74%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3050, 2970, 2870, 2810, 1615, 1450; δ_{H} (DMSO- d_6) 1.94 (4H, s, 2 \times CH₂), 3.30 (12H, s, 4 \times OCH₃), 4.15 (4H, s, 2 \times OCH₂), 5.51 [2H, s, 2 \times CH(OMe)₂], 7.39–7.43 [4H, m, 2 \times (H-5 + H-8)], 7.62 (2H, dd, J 8.5, 3.0 Hz, 2 \times H-7) and 8.29 (2H, s, 2 \times H-2).

10c : Yield 125 mg (93%); m.p. 110–112 °C; (Found : C, 64.82; H, 6.05. C₂₉H₃₂O₁₀ requires : C, 64.43; H, 5.97%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3079, 2943, 2870, 2831, 1652, 1612, 1471; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 1.65–1.71 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.86–1.93 (4H, m, 2 \times CH₂), 3.44 (12H, s, 4 \times OCH₃), 4.08 (4H, t, J 6.3 Hz, 2 \times OCH₂), 5.63 [2H, s, 2 \times CH(OMe)₂], 7.26 (2H, dd, J 9.0, 3.0 Hz, 2 \times H-7), 7.39 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, 2 \times H-8), 7.57 (2H, d, J 3.0 Hz, 2 \times H-5) and 8.10 (2H, s, 2 \times H-2).

Treatment of 3,3'-diformylbischromone 6 with Et₃N in dry methanol :

Bischromone **6** (0.3 mmol) was heated in dry methanol (20 ml) under reflux containing Et₃N (300 mg, 3 mmol) for 4 h. Methanol was removed from the reaction mixture and ice water was added to get a semisolid mass. It was extracted with CHCl₃, dried over Na₂SO₄ and chromatographed over silica gel (100–200) using 10% EtOAc in benzene as eluent to afford a white solid **11**. When the time was reduced from 4 h to 3 h, a small amount of **12a** was also isolated along with **11a** from the reaction mixture of **6a** and Et₃N.

11a : Yield 75 mg (70%); m.p. 168–170 °C; (Found : C, 69.43; H, 4.62. C₂₁H₁₆O₆ requires : C, 69.23; H, 4.43%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3077, 2925, 1652, 1470, 1313; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 2.33 (2H, quintet, J 6.0 Hz, CH₂), 4.27 (4H, t, J 6.0 Hz, 2 \times OCH₂), 6.32 (2H, d, J 6.1 Hz, 2 \times H-3), 7.28 (2H, dd, J 9.1, 3.0 Hz, 2 \times H-7), 7.41 (2H, d, J 9.1 Hz, 2 \times H-8), 7.59 (2H, d, J 3.0 Hz, 2 \times H-5) and 7.84 (2H, d, J 6.1 Hz, 2 \times H-2).

11b : Yield 85 mg (75%); m.p. 212–214 °C; (Found : C, 70.10; H, 4.85. C₂₂H₁₈O₆ requires : C, 69.83; H, 4.79%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3084, 2972, 2876, 1649, 1470, 1319; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 2.03 (4H, s, 2 \times CH₂), 4.14 (4H, s, 2 \times OCH₂), 6.32 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, 2 \times H-3), 7.27 (2H, dd, J 9.1, 2.9 Hz, 2 \times H-7), 7.40 (2H, d, J 9.1 Hz, 2 \times H-8), 7.56 (2H, d, J 2.9 Hz, 2 \times H-5) and 7.84 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, 2 \times H-2).

11c : Yield 85 mg (72%); m.p. 160–162 °C; (Found : C, 70.21; H, 5.26. C₂₃H₂₀O₆ requires : C, 70.40; H, 5.14%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3085, 2980, 2870, 1660, 1450, 1325;

δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 1.68–1.73 (2H, m, CH₂), 1.86–1.93 (4H, m, 2 \times CH₂), 4.09 (4H, t, J 6.0 Hz, 2 \times OCH₂), 6.32 (2H, d, J 5.9 Hz, 2 \times H-3), 7.25–7.28 (2H, m, 2 \times H-7), 7.39 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, 2 \times H-8), 7.56 (2H, d, J 3.0 Hz, 2 \times H-5) and 7.83 (2H, d, J 5.9 Hz, 2 \times H-2).

Synthesis of bischromone 11 from enaminketone 13 :

Enaminketone **13** (0.5 mmol) was heated under reflux in methanol (20 ml) containing one drop of H₂SO₄ for half an hour, when the yellow colour of the enaminketone **13** was found to disappear. A white solid was obtained on removing the solvent under reduced pressure. It was washed with water, dried in air and recrystallised from CHCl₃ to get **11a** (160 mg, 88%), **11b** (170 mg, 90%) and **11c** (180 mg, 92%) from **13a**, **13b** and **13c**, respectively.

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